

ALGORITHM FOR CALCULATING THE EXPERIMENTAL PLANTING APPARATUS OF THE POTATO PLANTER

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Abstract. The method of calculation of the conveyor-spoon planting apparatus of the potato planter, capturing sprouted potatoes from the pickling liquid, is presented. Expressions are obtained that allow optimizing the geometric parameters of the conveyor spoon of the planting apparatus, as well as its kinematic parameters, depending on the physic-mechanical properties of potato tubers and pickling liquid.

Key words: Spoon disembarking apparatus, drag, free surface, potato planter, transportation.

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Introduction

When planting sprouted potato tubers with the help of a potato planter, a technical solution is required that allows, on the one hand, to ensure the safety of the emerging sprouts, and on the other hand, to treat them [7]. The solution to this problem is a technological process that includes the supply of tubers from the hopper to the bucket feeder, pre-filled with dressing liquid, the capture of tubers by spoons of a two-row spoon-conveyor planter and the transportation of the tuber to the drop zone into the planting furrow [1]. As a dressing liquid, a solution of a contact fungicide in a saline solution is used, the density of which exceeds the specific gravity of the tubers and is 1.16 g/cm³.

The process of capturing potato tubers from a liquid medium requires the determination of the geometric and kinematic parameters of the conveyor landing apparatus, which ensure their reliable retention in the spoons, and, consequently, the prevention of skips during planting. In addition, it is important to study the process of interaction of a spoon with a liquid and determine the parameters of the least disturbing effect, which also determines the reliable capture of tubers.

Object and method of research

Repair Let us consider the interaction of a spoon having the shape of a truncated sphere with radius r and depth ℓ located radially relative to the center of rotation O' , rotating at a constant angular velocity ω with a stationary liquid in the receiving bucket. Let us determine the force P_x with which the liquid acts on the spoon.

We choose the XoY coordinate system (Figure 1) rigidly connected to the moving spoon. And consider the force of the liquid on a spoon that does not have holes [4]. We use the momentum change theorem: the change in the momentum of a fluid per unit time in a chosen direction is equal to the projection of all forces acting on the fluid in this direction or in differential form:

$$dP_x \cdot dt = d(mv)$$

After the calculations and transformations, an expression was obtained for determining the frontal force per spoon:

$$P_x = \rho \omega^2 y_c^2 S = \rho \omega^2 (R + a + r)^2 \pi r^2 \quad (1)$$

where: S is the area of the spoon on the line 1-1;

mustache- distance to the center of gravity of the volume of liquid inside the spoon;

R is the radius of the drive sprocket of the spoon conveyor drive;

a is the distance between the asterisk and the spoon.

Expression (1) shows that the force P_x , with which the liquid acts on the surface of the spoon, is determined by the speed $v_c = \omega y_c$ movement of its center, which is equivalent to a uniform flow around the spoon with a speed v_c .

For streamlined bodies, the force of resistance to movement (the drag force) tends to zero and is determined only by the friction forces that arise when the body moves in a fluid. For poorly streamlined bodies (such as our spoon), the drag force is much greater than the friction force, but it is less than the value determined by expression (1) and is found as follows:

Figure 1: Forces acting on a spoon as it moves through a liquid

$$P_x = C_x S_m \frac{\rho v_x^2}{2} = C_x \frac{P_x}{2} \quad (2)$$

where: C_x is the drag coefficient, determined empirically, and depends on the body shape, Reynolds number, flow angle and a number of other parameters;

S_m is the midsection area of the spoon.

For the first time such data are found in the works of Newton [2]. The drag coefficient according to Newton is 2.0 - this is the maximum possible theoretical value. However, if another body with the same midsection is installed in the aft part of the body, near it, then the total pressure resistance of the system of bodies decreases.

During the search experiments, the resistance of 2 variants of spoons was determined: straight and reverse spoons with solid bottoms, and straight and reverse spoons with side holes in the first one, at the point of their connection there was one common central hole. For simplicity, the figures do not show the reverse spoon [5].

For poorly streamlined bodies, the force of pressure on the aft part depends on the conditions of the flow around the body, i.e. its shape, which determines the separation of the flow from the body and the formation of vortices behind it (the shape of the vortex wake) and will always be less than the pressure force on the frontal part of the body. As a result, a resulting pressure force arises,

which determines the magnitude of the frontal resistance to movement. In our case, a reverse spoon is installed behind the straight spoon, located in the back of the first.

Then the force of resistance to the movement of the straight and reverse spoons of the first variant can be written as:

$$P_x = C_x S \frac{\rho v_c^2}{2} = C_x \frac{1}{2} \rho \omega^2 (R + a + r)^2 \pi r^2 \quad (3)$$

where the drag coefficient can be taken, according to Newton's calculations, $C_x \leq 1,43$.

Consider the second version of the spoons with central and side holes.

Let us take into account the influence of the holes in the spoon on the magnitude of the force P_x . If there are holes in the spoon, the total area s_0 of the momentum will be equal to:

$$\rho Q_{oms} v_c = \rho \mu_0 s_0 v_c \cdot v_c = \rho \mu_0 s_0 v_c^2$$

Where: μ_0 - hole flow rate,

Q_{otv} - fluid flow through the holes.

$$\text{Then } P_x = \rho \omega^2 y_c^2 S - \rho \mu_0 s_0 \omega^2 y_c^2 = \rho \omega^2 y_c^2 (S - \mu_0 s_0)$$

$$\text{or } P_x = \rho \omega^2 y_c^2 S \left(1 - \mu_0 \frac{s_0}{S}\right)$$

$$\text{Where } P_x = \rho \omega^2 (R + a + r)^2 \pi r^2 \left[1 - \mu_0 \frac{n r_{oms}^2}{r^2}\right]$$

where: r_{otv} is the radius of a single hole;

n is the number of holes.

The drag force in this case will be equal to:

$$P_x = C_x \frac{P_x}{2} = \frac{1}{2} C_x S \omega^2 (R + a + r)^2 \pi r^2 \left[1 - \mu_0 n \left(\frac{r_{oms}}{r}\right)^2\right] \quad (4)$$

The orifice flow rate μ_0 depends on the Reynolds number:

$$Re = \frac{v_c d_{oms}}{\nu}$$

At $Re > 102$ the value $\mu_0 \approx 0,62 - 0,65$ [3].

The planting rate and productivity of the potato planter depends on the linear speed of the planter conveyor.

With the hole diameter $d_{ot} = 0.005$ m and the calculated conveyor speed $v_c = 0.5$ m/s, we have:

$$Re = \frac{0,5 \cdot 0,005}{1 \cdot 10^{-6}} = 2500.$$

Holes in the blade are necessary to prevent additional flow of the dressing liquid into the furrow, although the presence of holes in them can affect the drag coefficient C_x upwards.

However, still the value $C_x \leq 2,0$.

At the moment the spoon of the planting machine conveyor reaches the surface of the dressing liquid, there is a danger of the tuber "ejecting" beyond its limits [6]. Let us determine the conditions under which the captured tuber will be securely held in the spoon.

We assume that the tuber is a ball with an equivalent radius r_2 . In a static state, being on the liquid surface (Fig. 2), the tuber is under the action of the weight G and the Archimedean force R_A .

Figure 2: Scheme for determining the forces acting on a tuber immersed in a liquid

The equilibrium condition with respect to the vertical axis Z has the form:

$$G = P_A. \quad (5)$$

We have:

$$G = \rho_T g W_T = \rho_T g \frac{4}{3} \pi r_2^3$$

$$P_A = \rho g W_{nozp}$$

Where: ρ_T And ρ - the density of the tuber and liquid, respectively;

W_{nozp} - the volume of the immersed part of the tuber.

$$\text{We get: } 4r_2^3 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_T}{\rho}\right) = h_1^2 (3r_2 - h_1) \quad (6)$$

Expression (6) makes it possible to determine the exit of the tuber to the surface of the liquid h_1 at a given value of the ratio ρ_T/ρ and the value of the radius r_2 . In a static state, the tuber is under the action of the fluid pressure force, the value of which at an arbitrary point on the tuber surface is $P_{st} = \rho gh$. The result of the action of the static pressure force on the surface of the tuber abc immersed in the liquid is the Archimedean force R_A , which balanced the weight of the tuber G .

When the rotating spoon approaches the tuber, a part of its surface abc is immersed inside the spoon (Figure 3). The cross section of the tuber at the level of the site 1-1 is at this moment the area S_1 . And on the surface of the spoon, in addition to the forces of static pressure, hydrodynamic pressure forces begin to act, which are projected onto the vertical direction Z and cause the tuber to rise above the free surface of the liquid (an increase in h_1)

Figure 3: Scheme for determining the forces when the spoon approaches the tuber and exits to the free surface

The hydrodynamic pressure at an arbitrary point of the liquid inside the spoon 1 will be equal to:

$$P_{zu\delta p} = P_y + P_\delta = \rho v^2 = \rho \omega^2 y^2$$

where: P_c - centrifugal pressure $P_y = \rho \frac{\omega^2 y^2}{2} = \rho \frac{v^2}{2}$;

P_δ - additional dynamic pressure $P_\delta = \frac{\rho v^2}{2}$.

The maximum removal of the tuber on the free surface of the liquid h_1 at a given speed of movement v_c , the radius of the tuber r_2 and the value of ρ_T/ρ

can be determined from the expression:
$$v_c^2 = \frac{1}{3} g \left[\frac{h_1^2}{r_2^2} (3r_2 - h_1) - 4r_2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_T}{\rho} \right) \right] \quad (7)$$

given that $(r_2 < \ell; S_1 = \pi r_2^2; \beta = 0; \ell < \ell_1)$.

We determine from expression (7) the speed v_c at which the spoon approaches the surface of the liquid O-O, taking out the tuber by half ($h_1 = r_2$):

$$(v_c)_{r_2}^2 = \frac{4}{3} g r_2 \left(\frac{\rho_T}{\rho} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (8)$$

Assuming $r_2 = 0.025\text{m}$, $\rho_T/\rho = 1.15$. We get $(v_c)_{r_2} = 0.348\text{m/s}$

Let us take into account the influence of the holes in the spoon on the value of the hydrodynamic force P_{hydr} . The hydrodynamic pressure inside the spoon in the presence of holes will be equal to:

$$P_{zu\delta p} = \rho v'^2 = \rho v^2 \left[1 - \mu_o n \left(\frac{r_{oms}}{r} \right)^2 \right]^2 = \rho \omega^2 y^2 \left[1 - \mu_o n \left(\frac{r_{oms}}{r} \right)^2 \right]^2 \quad (9)$$

Expression (9) can be written as: $P_{zu\delta p} = \rho \omega_x^2 y^2$

$$\text{Where: } \omega_x = \omega \left[1 - \mu_o n \left(\frac{r_{ome}}{r} \right)^2 \right]^2,$$

the angular speed of the spoon reduced to the recalculated linear speed of movement v's.

In other words, the influence of the holes in the spoon can be reduced to a change (decrease) in its angular velocity ω . Physically, this means that each liquid particle in the volume of the spoon, due to the flow of holes, acquires a speed in the direction opposite to the rotation of the spoon. As a result, at an arbitrary point on the spoon, the velocity of the liquid particle will be equal to:

$$v' = v^2 \left[1 - \mu_o n \left(\frac{r_{ome}}{r} \right)^2 \right] \quad (10)$$

Thus, it is possible to consider all the obtained expressions both for a spoon with holes and without (including the acceleration of the inertial forces acting in the liquid by replacing the real angular velocity ω with the reduced ω_x). However, this does not apply to the spoon itself, as a mechanical object that rotates with an angular velocity ω . So, if a tuber sits on the bottom of a spoon, centrifugal forces determined by its angular velocity will act on it.

If the speed of the spoon is close to v_c , and its depth is $l \leq r_2$, then the tuber, when the spoon reaches the surface of the liquid, sits on the bottom of the spoon and the centrifugal force of inertia begins to act on it, as on a solid body, which tends to "throw" the tuber out of the spoon.

$$F_y = \rho_T W_T j_c = \frac{4}{3} \pi r_2^3 \rho_T \omega^2 y_c = \frac{4}{3} \pi r_2^3 \rho_T v_c \omega \quad (11)$$

where: j_c - acceleration of inertial forces $j_c = \omega^2 y_c = \frac{v_c^2}{y_c}$

At the same time, the centripetal force F_{uc} acts on the immersed part of the tuber

$$F_{uc} = \rho W_{noz p} j_{c'} = \frac{2}{3} \pi r_2^3 \rho \omega^2 y_{c'} \quad (12)$$

where $u_{s'}$ is the coordinate of the center of gravity of the immersed part of the tuber.

Taking $u_{s'} \approx u_s$, we get:

$$F_{uc} = \frac{2}{3} \pi r_2^3 \rho \omega^2 y_c = \frac{2}{3} \pi r_2^3 v_c \omega \rho \quad (13)$$

The centripetal force is due to the radial component of the force of hydrodynamic pressure on the surface of the tuber abc (centrifugation effect).

The effect of centrifugation is that heavy particles, when rotated together with the liquid, are thrown to the periphery, and light particles are thrown to the center of rotation. Heavy particles is a tuber located in a spoon. Then the resulting centrifugal force acting on the tuber will be equal to:

$$(F_y)_{pez} = F_y - F_{uc} = \frac{4}{3} \pi r_2^3 v_c \omega \rho_T \left(1 - \frac{\rho}{2\rho_T} \right) \quad (14)$$

Conclusions

The calculations performed show that the linear velocity of the spoons must be such that the balance of forces of the entire system is maintained. The ejection of the tuber from the spoon will not occur if the depth of the spoon is equal to the average radius r_2 , and the line of action of the resulting centrifugal force does not pass above point A (Figure 3).

The expressions obtained make it possible to optimize the geometric parameters of the planting machine conveyor spoon, as well as its kinematic parameters, depending on the physical and mechanical properties of potato tubers and dressing liquid.

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